

Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

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1. Objective

The objective of the stakeholder engagement strategy is to maximize the visibility of the METAPLANTCODE project and increase the quality of the output by actively involving relevant scientists, research organisations, and government agencies. Our goal is to promote collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, and increase the use of project results.

2. Stakeholder Identification

Primary Stakeholders

- Scientists in the fields of eDNA, metabarcoding, and plant research
- Research institutes and universities
- Biodiversity and conservation authorities
- Biomonitoring and environmental monitoring programs

Secondary Stakeholders

- Political decision-makers (EU, national environmental ministries, biodiversity programs)
- NGOs and conservation organizations
- Companies in the environmental technology and ecological services sectors
- Citizen science networks
- Data infrastructure initiatives (e.g., GBIF, ELIXIR)

3. Engagement Approaches & Communication Strategies

I. Increase Information & Visibility

- Supply instructional materials and project updates via our website

- Regular social media campaigns
- Create an interactive website with resources on protocols, databases, analysis pipelines, and member contacts
- Presentation of the project at conferences and workshops

II. Consultation & Collect Feedback

- Conduct stakeholder workshops and online surveys to identify areas needed to improve plant DNA metabarcoding
- actively communicate with interested stakeholders directly at international conferences

III. Promote Participation & Cooperation

- Build a researcher network that connects metabarcoding experts via slack or an alternative collaboration platform
- Encourage joint publications and research initiatives
- Provide a platform for data exchange & standardization

IV. Secure Long-Term Partnerships & Sustainability

- Cooperate with international research infrastructures such as GBIF and ELIXIR
- Explore and apply for funding opportunities for future projects

4. Evaluation of project success

- **Define KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):**
 - Assessment of engagement rates on social media
 - Participation in workshops
 - Number of citations & scientific collaborations
 - Number of conference visitations/METAPLANTCODE presentations
 - Number of publications
- **Collect Feedback:**
 - Surveys on the effectiveness of the methods developed by METAPLANTCODE
 - Interviews

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